

Report of Zoonoses, Alimentary and Water-Borne Infections in the Slovak Republic in 2021

1. *Salmonella* spp.

Salmonella has long been a zoonotic pathogen of high concern affecting both humans and animals. Its disease symptoms include nausea, diarrhoea, fever and abdominal cramps. The main sources of infection are eggs and undercooked food of animal origin, but there is also an upward trend in the risk of salmonella from keeping reptiles and exotic species. Across all European Union countries, in 2020 there were 52,702 cases, of which 57 ended in death.

There were 4,542 reported cases in Slovakia in 2021, which is 30.6% more than in 2020. No deaths were recorded. Cases were reported in all regions, with the highest morbidity being in the Prešov region. A total of 149 outbreaks were recorded, of which 21 were of a larger size. *S. Enteritidis* was the most common cause of infections and outbreaks. The most frequent transmission factor was home-laid eggs. A total of 9,082 food samples were analysed, of which 0.20% were positive. As in previous years, there was a higher rate of positive samples in broiler meat and products, though the prevalence decreased from 17.9% in the previous year to 4.7%. No evidence of salmonella was found in ice cream, frozen desserts, collective catering dishes, delicatessen products, confectionery or sweets. The most common serovars in food were *S. Enteritidis* (55.0%) and *S. Infantis* (35.0%). Tests were also carried out on live birds in 6,309 poultry flocks, with 0.3% positive results, dominated by the *S. Infantis* and *S. Enteritidis* serovars. Amongst other domestic animal and pet species, salmonella was isolated most frequently in reptiles and domestic carnivores. Of 427 animal feed samples tested, 0.94% were positive. Tests were carried out on 4,151 samples from the environment and water. *Salmonella* spp. was confirmed in 0.55% of samples from children's sandpits and 8.79% of surface water samples. It was not present in water from the public water supply, wells, watercoolers, mineral water or bottled water. Sanitary and environmental swabs were also negative for salmonella. There was one positive sample in 1,016 swabs taken from food establishments.

Fig. 1 Salmonellosis Incidence by District in 2021

A higher percentage of positive samples and various salmonella serovars were detected from the aquariums, water, bedding and swabs of turtles and exotic reptiles. Reptiles can be a source of salmonella even when they have no clinical symptoms. This makes them a high-risk pet especially for young children, pregnant women and immunocompromised people. Microbial resistance in *Salmonella* isolates is typically species specific. Tests were carried out on 12 isolates from carcasses and 2 isolates from the skin of pigs. Resistance of 40% was found only for Ampicillin and Tetracycline. Resistance to quinolones and fluoroquinolones was also low.

2. *Escherichia coli*

Escherichia coli is an important part of the intestinal microbiota in humans and other animals. Some of the most important strains of *E. coli* in relation to food poisoning are those that produce verocytotoxins / Shiga toxins (VTEC/STEC). They are transmitted through contaminated food and water, contact with animals and direct contact between people. The incubation period is 3 to 9 days. Haemolytic uremic syndrome (HUS), which is characterized by kidney failure and develops in 7% of VTEC/STEC infections, has an incubation period of up to 7 days.

In 2021 there were 235 reports of *E. coli* infection in Slovakia, the most common form being enteropathogenic *E. coli*. One minor outbreak was recorded. *E. coli* bacteria were detected in 2.8% of 4,690 food samples, mainly in nuts, oilseeds and cheeses made from raw milk. VTEC and other pathogenic strains were not identified in food. All strains suspected of being pathogenic were tested for the presence of genes encoding 13 serotypes. In one case, serotype O121 was detected. Since *E. coli* is one of the main indicators of water quality, tests were carried out on 16,781 water samples, in which there was a 7.48% positivity rate for *E. coli*. *E. coli* was most common in water used for leisure purposes. The bacteria were found in 56.8% of gravel pits. Tests on a total of 14,124 environmental swabs from various sources returned positive results in 2.6% of cases. There was relatively high positivity for children's sandpits – 11.7%. Swabs from food establishments had a 2.9% positivity rate. The level of microbial resistance in commensal *E. coli* taken from pig carcasses ranged from 0 to 42%. In 33% of samples, the bacteria were fully sensitive to the tested antimicrobials. *E. coli* able to produce extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) were detected in 58% of isolates. No carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* bacteria were detected in the isolates.

Samples of pork and beef from retail stores were tested for *E. coli* bacteria that produce ESBLs and carbapenemases. The prevalence of ESBL-producing *E. coli* in beef products is stable in a range between 3% (2015) and 7% (2021). In pork, however, there is a rising trend from 3% in 2015, through 11% in 2019 to 19% in 2021. Carbapenemase production has not yet been confirmed in any positive isolate.

Resistance was observed in three positive samples of wastewater, one sample of tarn water and one sample from a swimming pool. Ampicillin, gentamicin and tetracycline resistance were the main types.

3. *Yersinia* spp.

The genus *Yersinia* consists of 21 species of which 3 pathogenic for humans – *Y. pestis*, which is transmitted by fleas and causes plague, *Y. pseudotuberculosis*, the aetiological factor of pseudotuberculosis, and *Y. enterocolitica*, which mainly causes gastrointestinal disease. The main risk factors are undercooked pork, poultry, meat products, raw milk, infected plants, tofu, seafood and polluted water. It can also be transmitted from person to person. Yersinosis was the third-most frequently reported alimentary zoonosis in the EU in 2020, with 5,668 cases and 2 deaths. There were 16 recorded outbreaks in 6 EU countries.

In 2021 there were 210 cases in Slovakia, which is 26.5% more than in the previous year. There were 166 reported cases of illness in Slovakia in 2020. The age group with highest morbidity was children aged 0 – 4 years. Cases of illness were reported in every self-governing region with the highest morbidity in the Bratislava Region and the lowest in the Trnava Region.

Fig. 2 Incidence of Yersiniosis in Slovakia from 2007

Food was not tested for the presence of *Yersinia*. A total of 14 samples from animals with enteritis were tested for *Yersinia enterocolitica*. All the results were negative.

4. *Cronobacter* spp.

Cronobacter spp. is a genus of Gram-negative facultatively anaerobic bacteria. The species in this genus cause rare but life-threatening infections of infants. New-born babies with a low birth weight are the most vulnerable but the disease can also affect older people and immunocompromised people. Disease symptoms include irritability, jaundice, hoarse breathing, fluctuating body temperature. Meningitis can develop. Death occurs in 50% of new-born children within several hours or days. The main cause is contaminated dried baby formula.

No cases of human diseases were recorded in 2021. A total of 618 samples of first infant formula and follow-on formulas were specifically examined but the presence of *Cronobacter* spp was not confirmed.

5. *Shigella* spp.

The genus *Shigella* consists of rod-shaped bacteria belonging to the family *Enterobacteriaceae*, and is the causative agent of shigellosis, an intestinal infection. The characteristics of *Shigella* bacteria include adherence, invasion, intracellular reproduction and cell-to-cell spread. Infection is spread via the faecal-oral route, direct contact with infected individuals, contaminated food, water or objects.

In 2021 there were 130 reported cases of disease compared to 107 in 2020 for a year-on-year increase of 21.5%. The highest age-specific morbidity was in children aged 0 to 4 years. The causal agent was *Shigella flexneri* in 93 cases and *Shigella sonnei* in 36 cases.

As in the two previous years, no outbreaks were recorded. Food and water were not tested for the presence of *Shigella* spp.

6. *Plesiomonas shigelloides*

The genus *Plesiomonas* consists of a single species *Plesiomonas shigelloides*, which causes intestinal disease. Its clinical symptoms are fever, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, vomiting, nausea, chills and headache. Infection is spread via the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, contaminated food and from person to person.

Samples of surface water and the environment were not specifically tested for its presence in 2021, though the agent was sporadically isolated in examinations targeting the presence of other microorganisms in water and fish.

7. *Legionella* spp.

Legionella bacteria are part of the freshwater microbial ecosystems. They exist in symbiosis with other bacteria and amoebas, especially in biofilms. They also find good conditions for survival and reproduction in water supply systems. Researchers have identified 61 species of legionella, 28 of which are associated with human disease. A person becomes infected by inhaling a contaminated water aerosol. Infection can lead to a severe life-threatening pneumonia, Legionnaire's disease, which is fatal in 8 – 10% of cases, or an influenza-like disease, Pontiac fever.

Legionnaire's disease (LD) has been on the rise in Slovakia since 2014. In 2021 there were 148 cases of LD, 76% of which affected patients over the age of 50. In 51% of patients there was coinfection with the SARS-Cov-2 virus. The mortality rate for LD patients was 5%, which increased to 24% for patients with SARS-Cov-2 coinfection. Pontiac fever was diagnosed in 9 patients.

Tests for the presence of *Legionella* were carried out on 818 water samples, 170 swabs taken from the water environment and 61 air samples and swabs from air-conditioning equipment in the community and in health-care facilities. *Legionella*-contaminated water was found most frequently in hospitals (46.7%). Positive results were found in 13.6% of swab samples from the water environment and *Legionella* bacteria were not detected in any of the air samples or swabs from air conditioning equipment. The most common bacterium types were *L. pneumophila* serogroups 6, 9, 3, 1, 2. Epidemiological investigations to establish evidence of source were carried in the case of six patients with confirmed LD from Slovakia and four patients reported as travel-associated legionellosis from abroad. Matches were found between *Legionella* bacteria in the clinical and environmental samples on the level of species and serogroup for five of the patients from Slovakia. The investigations connected with foreigners' stays in Slovakia detected *Legionella* in accommodation facilities in three cases.

8. *Vibrio* spp.

Vibrio is a genus of bacteria that move using a whip-like appendage. As pathogens, the most severe risk is associated with *Vibrio cholerae* serotypes O1 and O139, which produce the cholera toxin and cause cholera epidemics. Thanks to rigorous hygiene, cholera has not been endemic in Europe for a long time and it occurs only as an imported infection. Serotypes of *V. cholerae* non O1 non O139 cause diarrhoeic diseases. People can become infected during recreational activity in water or through the food chain. The genus *Vibrio* includes another 12 species that can cause disease in humans, including *V. vulnificus*, which causes gastroenteritis, *V. parahaemolyticus* which causes alimentary intoxication, *V. fluvialis* and *V. furnissii*, which cause infection of skin, wounds and soft tissues.

As in previous years, there was no report of cholera in Slovakia in 2021. There was a case of severe diarrhoeic disease caused by *V. furnissii*. Tests were carried out on 18 foodstuffs without any positive finding. *Vibrio* bacteria were not found in mineralised pool waters. Several species were found in surface water for recreational bathing, especially in warm water during the summer season. The presence of *V. cholerae* and regular findings of *V. fluvialis* and *V. furnissii* in the water in Slovakia is a cause for concern because these pathogens are usually found in coastal areas and their appearance in our territory is probably linked to the warming climate.

9. *Aeromonas* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Aeromonas* live in wastewater, in soil and organic matter residues. They can also survive in chlorinated drinking water or colonise the intestinal tracts of various animals. They are pathogens for humans and animals. They cause disease by releasing a cytotoxic enterotoxin and through surface adhesion and invasion. *Aeromonas*-induced disease may present as a gastrointestinal or extraintestinal infection.

In 2021, the Regional Public Health Authority in Komárno analysed 51 isolates from the stools of patients with severe diarrhoeic disease. *Aeromonas* bacteria were detected in 37 cases, with 35% of cases being *A. caviae*. There were also two cases of extraintestinal infection involving *A. caviae*. Water samples revealed 46 strains. *A. hydrophila* accounted for 67.4% of these findings.

10. *Campylobacter* spp.

The genus *Campylobacter* can cause intestinal infections in people and miscarriages in livestock. These bacteria have reservoirs in the digestive tracts of domestic and wild animals. The transmission route can be faecal-oral, person-to-person, sexual contact or the consumption of contaminated food or water. The infective dose is relatively low. The incubation period is 2–5 days. The most common clinical symptoms are diarrhoea, abdominal pain, fever, headache

and muscle pain and possibly also vomiting. After recovering from acute enteritis, patients may develop neurological disorders. Campylobacteriosis has been the most commonly reported gastrointestinal disease in the EU since 2005, and in Slovakia since 2011.

There were 6,140 reported cases of campylobacteriosis in 2021. The highest incidence was in the Bratislava Region. The infection was imported in 8 cases. The authorities recorded 49 minor outbreaks involving 2 – 4 cases and 5 larger outbreaks involving 5 or more cases. The most frequent agent in these infections and outbreaks was *C. jejuni*. Out of 556 tested food samples, the presence of *Campylobacter* spp. was confirmed only in one sample of broiler meat. Of 1,331 samples of clinical material from animals tested for the presence of *Campylobacter* spp., 9.5 % tested positive. The main pathogenic agent in pigs was *C. coli*, which made up 94.1% of positive porcine samples. *C. jejuni* was the most common *Campylobacter* species in pets, having an incidence of 54.5% in cats and 76.9% in dogs.

Levels of microbial resistance ranged from 0% to 90%. None of the isolates were resistant to Chloramphenicol but there were high levels of resistance to Tetracycline 90% and Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin 71%.

11. *Brucella* spp.

Bacteria from the genus *Brucella* are the cause of the zoonotic disease brucellosis. The source of infection is an infected animal or on rare occasions a person and it is transmitted through direct contact with the infectious animal, contaminated food or an inhaled aerosol. Typical foods for the alimentary route of infection are meat, raw milk and products made from them. After penetrating the skin, mucous membranes or digestive tract, the *Brucella* bacteria multiply in the lymph nodes and then attack other organs through the bloodstream. The pathogenicity of these bacteria is determined by endotoxins. In 2020, there were 128 reported cases of brucellosis in European Union countries and two reported deaths. The pathogenic agent was *Brucella melitensis* in 88% of cases.

In the 10 years before 2020, no more than 1 case per year was reported in Slovakia and then in 2020 there were 7 infections with disease. In 2021 there were 6 reported cases, with the largest number in the Banská Bystrica Region. Slovakia is officially free of the incidence of bovine, ovine and caprine brucellosis. In order to maintain this status, 42,461 serological tests of cattle and 16,548 serological tests of sheep and goats were carried out. From 5,160 serological tests on pigs, the positive rate was 0.85%.

12. *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*

A. phagocytophilum is a species of bacteria in the genus *Rickettsiales*, which is a cause of granulocytic anaplasmosis in humans and animals. The primary vector is the tick *Ixodes ricinus*. The bacteria attack granulocytes (white blood cells) in the host's blood and undermine their immune system. The incubation period is 1 – 3 weeks from the tick bite. Symptoms of infection include headache, muscle pain, sweating, weakness and a high temperature. In animals, it causes granulocytic anaplasmosis of dogs and horses while in ruminants it causes tick-borne fever.

Biological samples from patients and animals were examined at the Institute of Virology and the Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences. *A. phagocytophilum* was detected in HIV patients with a prevalence of 12.4%. *A. phagocytophilum* was detected in the blood of two patients with diagnosis A 79.9 based on laboratory PCR. A high prevalence of infection was observed in cervine animals (72%), but blood samples from dogs were negative. The overall prevalence in human-biting ticks was 24.54%.

13. *Coxiella burnetii*

The intracellular bacteria *C. burnetii* are a pathogenic agent for the zoonotic disease Q fever. The main source of human infection are ruminants. Infection most often occurs through

inhalation of contaminated aerosols or dust, contact with infected animals or consumption of contaminated milk. The incubation period of the disease is 20 days. The acute form can produce high fever, headaches, weakness and shivering. It has fatal consequences in 2% of cases. There is also a less common chronic form that is associated with complications such as endocarditis or liver disorders.

There were 2 reported cases of Q fever in 2021. Both were from the Bratislava Region. The mechanism of transmission was unknown in one case, and in the other it was a tick bite. The BMC Institute of Virology at the Slovak Academy of Sciences tested serum samples from 267 patients. Values for the presence of antibodies against *Coxiella burnetii* phase II indicated that one of the tested patients had had Q fever in the past and six of them had acute Q fever. A total of 1,191 samples from cattle, goats and sheep were examined. Positive serological results were obtained only for cattle – 3.17%. There have been no positive serological findings in goats in recent years (most recently in 2010 and 2013) while there have long been no serological positive findings in sheep.

14. *Francisella tularensis*

Tularaemia, a zoonotic disease with natural foci, is caused by *Francisella tularensis*, a tiny, facultatively intracellular Gram-negative bacterium. In its natural foci, this pathogen circulates among various species of reservoir animals. Transmission can occur through direct or indirect contact with an infected animal, inhalation of contaminated dust or aerosols, ingestion of insufficiently cooked products from infected animals, contaminated water, food, ticks and stinging insects. The disease has a varied clinical picture. Its symptoms include fever, headache and muscle or joint pain amongst others. The incubation period of tularaemia is 3 – 8 days.

Compared to 2020, when 12 cases of tularaemia were reported in Slovakia, and 2019, when there were 20 cases, the incidence was lower in 2021 with no cases of tularaemia being reported in Slovakia. No outbreak of tularaemia in rabbits was recorded in 2021 either. The Institute of Epidemiology of the Faculty of Medicine at Comenius University, in cooperation with the Veterinary and Food Institute in Bratislava, monitored the prevalence of agglutination antibodies against *F. tularensis* in domestic animals from areas where it is endemic in western Slovakia. Tests carried out on 329 horses from four self-governing regions were serologically positive in 44.07% of cases. The highest positivity rate was in the Bratislava Region (51.63%). Surveillance results point to the persistence of natural foci of tularaemia with circulation of *F. tularensis* in the endemic region of western Slovakia.

15. *Leptospira* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Leptospira* are spiral-shaped Gram-negative bacteria that cause the zoonotic disease leptospirosis. The most important *Leptospira* reservoirs are rodents, cattle and pigs. Animal infections are mostly asymptomatic, though it can cause abortions or sterility in cattle and pigs. Infected animals shed *Leptospira* bacteria in their urine for months or years. Humans can be infected directly, through contact with an infected animal, or indirectly, for example through urine-contaminated water or soil. Leptospirosis can take the form of life-threatening hepatitis, meningitis, or flu-like diseases but it may also manifest as a subclinical infection. In severe cases, the disease can be fatal.

In 2021, three patients with leptospirosis were reported in Slovakia: one from the Nitra Region and two from the Banská Bystrica Region. All the patients were men who were infected with *Leptospira* bacteria from the serogroup *Sejroe* and serovar *Sorexjalna*. The patients had the respiratory and icteric (jaundice) form of the disease with both mild and severe courses.

A total of 694 animal blood samples were analysed, of which 3.6% were positive. From the tested animals, there were positive samples among cattle, pigs, sheep and dogs. The highest positivity rate was recorded in pigs (22.41%).

16. *Borrelia* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Borrelia* are spirochetes that cause diseases in humans and animals. They are classified into three groups by disease and vector. Bacteria in the first group causes relapsing fever and are transmitted by soft ticks or lice. Another group makes up the species complex *Borrelia burgdorferi* sensu lato, the causative agent of Lyme disease. The vectors of this group are hard ticks. The disease affects multiple systems within the human organism and is noted for the high variability of its clinical symptoms. The third group in the genus *Borrelia* consists of bacteria species which are phylogenetically close to those in the first group, but which are transmitted by hard ticks. In this case, the disease symptoms are fever, fatigue, joint pain and neurological symptoms.

In 2021, there were 621 reported illnesses in Slovakia, which is 35% less than in 2020 (when 961 illnesses were reported). The most reported infections came from the Trnava Region. The reported causes were tick bites in 343 cases and insect bites in 101 cases.

Fig. 3 Incidence and Trend of Lyme disease in Slovakia

Serological testing was carried out on 22 samples of dog blood and one sample of deer blood. Only the dogs had positive results (17.3% positivity rate).

Compared to previous years, the positivity rate in human-biting ticks was significantly higher in 2021, rising from a positivity rate of 27.2% in 2020 to 41.4% in 2021. In a population of 703 ticks collected from selected locations in the Komárno district, *B. burgdorferi* s.l. had a prevalence of 8.82%.

17. Chlamydia

Chlamydia are parasitic microorganisms that multiply in the cytoplasm of vertebrate cells and are the causative agents of the zoonotic disease chlamydiosis. Infections can result in varied symptoms (inflammation of the serous membrane, mucous membranes, lungs, joints, reproductive organs and nervous system). Infection during pregnancy is especially dangerous. In animals, chlamydia cause disease in both birds and mammals. *Chlamydia abortus* is one of the most dangerous pathogens in Slovakia, which can cause miscarriages and foetal losses in sheep, goats and cows, and can also infect humans and pose a threat to pregnancy. Transmission is possible through direct contact with animals, contact with their secretions, or by breathing in a contaminated aerosol.

No cases of mammal chlamydiosis or ornithosis (psittacosis), were reported in humans in 2021. It continues the trend of the preceding years. No human illness has been reported since 2009, with the exception of 2013 and 2015. Serum samples from 228 animals were tested for the presence of chlamydia antibodies in 2021. The positivity rate was 4.38%. No abortions caused by *Chlamydia abortus* were confirmed at cattle and sheep farms. On one goat farm the occurrence of chlamydiosis was suspected based on serological diagnostics.

18. *Mycobacterium* spp.

Pathogenic species from the genus *Mycobacterium* are the causative agents of tuberculosis in humans and animals. Zoonotic potential comes mainly from the complex *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Bacteria from a sick person or animal can be transmitted through the respiratory tract, contaminated food, direct contact with injured skin or through the mucous membranes. Many cases of disease are recorded in high-risk groups such as homeless people, migrants, prisoners, ethnic minorities, persons with HIV, alcoholics, drug addicts and other marginalised groups.

There were 137 reported cases of tuberculosis in Slovakia in 2021, which is 21 cases less than in 2020. The patients were aged 0 to 19 years in 40% of cases. As in previous years, the highest morbidity was recorded in eastern Slovakia and the lowest was in the Trenčín Region.

Fig. 4 Incidence of Tuberculosis in Regions of Slovakia and Surrounding Countries in 2021

Regarding animal health, the Slovak Republic continues to have the official status of a country free of bovine tuberculosis. Of 25 examined samples (from ibex, domestic hens, pigeons), 2 tested positive for *Mycobacterium avium*.

19. *Listeria* spp.

Listeria monocytogenes is the only known pathogenic species in this genus. It causes the zoonotic disease listeriosis, which has a high mortality rate. Rodents are a reservoir of listeria in the wild. The most common transmission pathway for humans is the consumption of contaminated food, especially raw or uncooked food. The disease presents with flu-like symptoms including fever, muscle aches and gastrointestinal discomfort. Due to the long incubation period, it is often very difficult to determine the source of infection. In 2020, there were 16 reported food-borne listeriosis outbreaks in the EU in which 120 people became ill. The outbreaks were mainly connected to fish.

There were 14 reports of disease in Slovakia in 2021 (morbidity rate 0.26/100,000), which is 7 more than in 2020. There were also 2 reports of neonatal listeriosis. The Bratislava Region had the most cases. The reports of neonatal listeriosis came from the Bratislava and Košice Regions. Tests were carried out on 5,222 samples from 31 types of food in 2021. The positivity rate was 0.67%. There was a higher positivity rate for the soft sheep's cheese *bryndza*. In animals, the only positive findings were in cattle, where 15.62% of samples were positive.

Tests for listeria were carried out on 1,735 environmental swabs with a 0.63% positivity rate. In 2021, as in previous years, the most frequently isolated serotype in food was serotype 1/2a, which accounted for 57%. Although serotype 1/2a is the most frequently isolated serotype from food, serotype 4b causes most human outbreaks. It accounted for 21% of the total number of serotypes from food.

20. *Bacillus anthracis*

Bacteria of the species *Bacillus anthracis* are the causative agent of splenic anthrax, which is a primary disease of ruminants, but can affect all mammals, including humans. Anthrax spores can survive in the environment for more than 100 years, making contaminated soil or animal raw materials a permanent source of infection. The human disease varies according to the site of infection and has three main forms – skin, gastrointestinal and pulmonary. Anthrax is a rare disease in EU countries.

Between 2016 and 2021, EU/EEC countries reported 22 cases of the disease. In June 2022, 100 cattle died from anthrax in Croatia and 6 people became infected.

The last cases of anthrax in Slovakia were in 2003 for humans and in 2014 for animals. In 2021, tests were carried out on 17 samples of raw materials from the leather industry with a negative result and on 3 suspect packages, none of which were found contain spores of *B. anthracis*.

21. *Clostridium* spp.

The bacterial genus *Clostridium* causes various types of disease in humans and animals. The basis of this pathogenicity is the production of exotoxins. *Cl. botulinum* is the causative agent of botulism in humans and animals. Death occurs on the 2nd to 5th day after ingestion; the mortality rate is 17 – 80%. In 2020, there were 80 cases of botulism in 12 EU countries, including 46 in Italy. *Cl. perfringens* is a common cause of food poisoning. The incubation period is 6 – 24 hours. The disease symptoms are cramps, diarrhoea and sometimes fever and vomiting. *Cl. perfringens* causes intestinal diseases in animals, especially young ones. Another group of clostridia cause wound infections. These include *Cl. perfringens*, *Cl. septicum*, *Cl. histolyticum*, *Cl. Novyi*, *Cl. sordelli* and *Cl. tetany*.

No human disease caused by *Cl. botulinum* or *Cl. perfringens* was reported in Slovakia in 2021. There were 5,100 cases of enterocolitis caused by *Cl. difficile*, which is an increase of 42.9% compared to 2020. Cases were reported in all self-governing regions. The highest morbidity rate was in the Prešov Region. Deaths were reported in 32 cases. Most cases of disease (81.5 %) were acquired in hospital. One case was imported from Gambia. There were 6 major outbreaks and 2 minor outbreaks.

A total of 462 food types were tested for *Cl. perfringens*, which was detected in 0.86% of samples.

Out of 2,589 food samples tested for the presence of *sulphite-reducing clostridia* only 1 fast-food sample was positive. Of 1,663 samples from clinically ill or dead animals tested for *Clostridium* spp., 62.2% were positive. Tests for *Clostridium* spp. were also carried out on 177 samples of animal feed. The positivity rate was 8.5%, mainly due to feed mixtures made from cereals. As *Cl. perfringens* is an indicator parameter for faecal water pollution, 875 samples of water were tested for its presence. None of the samples of bottled, spring, mineral and infant water tested positive. *Cl. perfringens* was detected in drinking water and feedwater. Tests for *sulphite-reducing clostridia* were carried out on 283 water samples. The bacteria were detected in 23.3% of samples, whereas all positive findings were in surface water samples, where 82.5% of the 80 examined samples were positive.

22. *Staphylococcus aureus* (coagulase positive staphylococci and their toxins)

Staphylococcus aureus is a Gram-positive coccus bacterium that is found in more than 50% of healthy people. In addition to causing infections in its own right, it also produces pathogenic toxins. The consumption of food containing staphylococcal enterotoxins is a cause of food poisoning. All kinds of contaminated food can be a source of disease but especially food for direct consumption rich in proteins. In 2020, there were 43 outbreaks in EU countries caused by toxins from *Staphylococcus aureus*.

No cases of unspecified intestinal infection caused by *S. aureus* bacteria were reported in 2021. A total of 11,073 food samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci. The set limits were exceeded in 1.33% of samples. Food types that exceeded the limits at higher rates included breast milk (8.64%) and milk and milk products (8.38%). Staphylococcal enterotoxin was not detected in any of the samples.

Enterotoxin production was demonstrated in 17.86 % of isolates from food, with breast milk having the highest positivity rate. Regarding clinically ill animals, tests on 2,598 samples for *S. aureus* returned a 16.89% positivity rate. Out of 18,927 samples of water and environmental swabs, *S. aureus* was detected in 1.94%, most positive findings were from in swabs from hospitals. Toxin-producing isolates were also most likely to be found on swabs from the hospital environment.

Antimicrobial resistance was monitored in 509 samples from food, animals, water and the environment. Resistance was observed in 15.32% of samples. In food, 16.35% of the isolates with a positive finding were methicillin-resistant *S. aureus*, the highest rate of resistance was found in pork – 32.84%. In 106 samples from various animal species, methicillin resistance was detected in 4.72% of *S. aureus* isolates, especially isolates originating from dairy cows.

Resistance to methicillin was examined in 224 isolates from water and the environment, of which 15.63% were resistant. No resistance was detected in isolates from water and swabs from food establishments. Swabs from mobile phones and public transport detected *S. aureus* with resistance against several antibiotics, especially penicillin, ceftiofur and chloramphenicol.

23. *Enterococcus* spp.

Enterococcus spp. is a genus of Gram-positive cocci made up of more than 50 species, many of which belong to the normal intestinal microbiota of humans and animals. Some species are causative agents of urogenital tract infections, bacteraemia, endocarditis, and infections of pelvic soft tissue and postoperative wounds. Because enterococci have both natural and acquired resistance against antibiotics, they represent a high risk in hospitals.

While *E. faecalis* is the more frequently detected species, *E. faecium* is more problematic because of its resistance, especially to vancomycin. In veterinary medicine, this trend is not yet as pronounced as in human medicine, but the incidence of urinary tract infections caused by enterococci is increasing. The presence of enterococci in water is one of the indicators of faecal contamination.

In 2021, there were 72 cases of diseases caused by *Enterococcus* bacteria. The most frequently isolated species was *E. faecium* and all cases were acquired in health-care facilities. Testing of 63 samples of food found positive results in 11.1 % of samples. The categories with the highest percentage of positive samples were powders of plant and insect origin. Of 13 examined animal feeds, almost half (46.1%) contained enterococci. Of 14,880 water samples, 6.4% were above the limit or positive. Of 12,173 samples from the environment, 1.8 % showed the presence of the genus *Enterococcus* spp.; the most positive samples were from sandpits and packaging material.

Enterococci resistant to antibiotics were present in both wastewater and surface water samples as well as plant and insect powders. Resistance to ampicillin and vancomycin predominated.

24. Lyssavirus

Rabies is caused by RNA viruses from the genus Lyssavirus. This disease affects all types of warm-blooded animals and is transmissible to humans. After penetrating the body, it spreads to the central nervous system, where it multiplies and causes inflammation of the brain, from which it later continues through nerve fibres to the salivary glands and saliva. The incubation period is 1 to 3 months. Among animals, foxes are particularly susceptible to rabies. Disease

surveillance is comprehensive in all member states of the European Union on a passive basis, except in the Czech Republic, Portugal and Slovakia, where surveillance is on an active basis.

The most recent case of rabies in humans in any EU Member State was in 2020. The last Slovak case was recorded 30 years earlier, in 1990. Rabies was last diagnosed in an animal in Slovakia in 2015. Animals were tested 919 times in 2021. In all tests, the results were negative. As an eradication programme measure, 735,592 vaccination doses were laid for oral vaccination of foxes.

25. Influenza virus

Influenza is among the oldest infectious and transmissible diseases of humans and animals. It is caused by an RNA virus. The most dangerous group are the type A influenza viruses that infect humans, several species of mammals and a wide variety birds. The genus *Influenza virus A* also includes avian influenza viruses with reservoirs in waterfowl. The infection causes a wide spectrum of symptoms in birds, from a mild course to a highly contagious and rapidly fatal disease.

In 2021, 40,763 people fell ill with flu and flu-like illnesses, with the highest incidence being in the Trnava Region. Age-specific morbidity was highest in the 0 to 5-year-old age group and lowest in people over 60. The aetiology was dominated by unspecified influenza A virus infections over unspecified influenza B viruses. The VI in Zvolen tested 2,146 blood samples from 133 poultry farming holdings without any positive findings. Tests for the nucleic acid of avian flu virus were carried out on 79 samples from birds living in the wild and 53 samples from domestic poultry. Positive results were recorded for 29 samples.

26. Tick-borne encephalitis virus

Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) is a viral disease affecting humans and warm-blooded animals. Its incubation period is 7 to 28 days. The disease usually has a two-phase clinical course. The first phase resembles flu and is followed by a symptom-free period lasting 1 – 20 days. Typical second-phase symptoms are headaches, photophobia, double vision and vomiting. The mortality rate is 2%, and almost 10% of patients subsequently suffer from various neurological problems. TBEV has its reservoirs in rodents and it is transmitted by ticks. TBEV can also be transmitted via the alimentary route, for example through milk from infected animals.

In 2021, there were 92 cases of Central European tick-borne encephalitis, which is 50.3% less than in 2020. The highest age-specific morbidity was in people aged 45 to 64 years. The most common cause was tick bite (48 cases). There were infections in all regions of Slovakia except the Bratislava Region. One outbreak was reported from the Prešov region, the source of which was untreated goat's milk from a farm.

Fig. 5 Incidence of Tick-Borne Encephalitis in Slovakia in 2021

Food testing examined 126 samples, of which 4.76% were positive (3 pool samples of goat's milk and 3 pool samples of sheep's milk). Three foci of TBEV were identified (Turčianske Teplice, Púchov, Zvolen). Serological examinations were conducted on 38 samples from goats (21.05% positive) and 393 samples from wild birds, from which 8 blackbirds (2%) were seropositive. The BMC Institute of Virology at the Slovak Academy of Sciences examined 78 human-biting ticks, 2.56% of which were found to be infected with TBEV.

27. West Nile virus

WNV is the causative agent of West Nile fever. Birds are the reservoir and main host of the virus, while various types of mosquitoes that suck the infected blood of birds serve as vectors. Humans and horses can also be hosts, but the virus cannot be transmitted from them to other vectors. Infection can also develop after organ transplantation, blood transfusion, or through the placenta. The incubation period is 2 – 15 days. Most infections are asymptomatic; about 20% of patients develop flu-like symptoms. In a few cases, serious symptoms such as encephalitis, meningoencephalitis or meningitis may develop. Elderly and immunocompromised individuals are at higher risk of developing severe symptoms. In 2021, there were 139 cases of human infection in the EU/EEA, ten of which were fatal.

In 2021, no human cases of West Nile fever were reported in Slovakia, nor was there any report of acute WNV infection in horses.

28. Dengue virus

Dengue fever is caused by a virus whose vector is the mosquito species *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*. Its incubation period is 3 to 14 days. The disease may have a febrile course or it may appear as a haemorrhagic fever. In 1970, Dengue fever was endemic only in 9 countries outside Europe.

Dengue fever was not reported in Slovakia in 2021. The cases of the disease reported in recent years were all imported

29. Hantaan virus

Hantaviruses cause haemorrhagic fevers in humans but are not transmissible from person to person. Their reservoir is rodents, which shed the virus through urine, faeces and saliva. Humans usually become infected by inhaling contaminated dust. In Europe, including Slovakia, there are several types of hantaviruses that cause this disease, the most common causative agent is the Puumala virus, which causes disease with a mild course. A more severe form of disease is associated with the Dobrava-Belgrade virus, which can sometimes be fatal.

In 2021, there were 117 reported cases in Slovakia, which is a 2.34-fold increase compared to the previous year (50 cases of disease were reported in 2020). Cases occurred in all age groups except children aged 0 to 9 years. The regions with the most cases were the Prešov and Košice Regions.

30. Norwalk virus

Norwalk virus (NoV) is a small, highly contagious virus whose only reservoir is humans. Transmission takes place through the faecal-oral route or contaminated food and drinks. The incubation period is from 12 to 72 hours, the disease is manifested by severe watery diarrhoea, vomiting, nausea, abdominal pain and high temperature. Symptoms last 1 to 3 days. Uncooked foods are especially risky. In 2020, NoV was the fourth most frequently reported agent responsible for outbreaks in EU countries, causing a total of 130 outbreaks in 13 Member States in which 2,633 people became ill.

In Slovakia, 1,785 cases of Norwalk-related illness were reported, which is twice as many as in the previous year. The highest morbidity was in children aged 0 – 4 years. There were 41

outbreaks, of which 13 were of a larger size. Nosocomial infection was reported in 120 cases. Eight samples from sheep were tested for the virus, all having negative results.

31. Rotavirus

Rotavirus is an RNA virus that mutates and recombines easily, is stable and capable of rapid multiplication. It can survive in the air and on contaminated surfaces for several days. It is transmitted through the faecal-oral route, through consumption of contaminated food, or contact with contaminated objects. Its incubation period is 1 to 3 days. Early symptoms include fever, vomiting and abdominal pain. Children under the age of five are at high risk from the disease. The best form of protection against infection is vaccination.

There were 3,143 cases of illness caused by intestinal infection with rotavirus in 2021. A total of 70 outbreaks were recorded, of which 13 were of a larger size. Food and water were not tested for the presence of the virus.

32. Hepatitis A virus – HAV

Hepatitis A virus (HAV) is a causative agent of acute inflammatory liver disease whose main reservoir is humans. The infection spreads through the faecal-oral route or contaminated water and food.

Since 2020, a significant decrease in morbidity has been observed, which is probably related to preventative measures, including those against COVID 19. In 2021 there were 12 cases of Hepatitis A disease in Slovakia and no outbreaks. No food samples were tested for the presence of HAV.

33. Hepatitis E virus – HEV

Hepatitis E is an infectious viral liver disease that spreads through the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, food and transfusions. Its incubation period ranges from 14 to 70 days. The most common route of HEV transmission is the consumption of raw or under-cooked pork, venison, liver and products made from them.

In 2021 there were 54 reported cases. The self-governing regions with the most cases were Banská Bystrica and Prešov. The University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice tested 165 samples of pork meat and liver taken at slaughterhouses for the presence of HEV. There was no finding of HEV in the pork meat, but HEV RNA was found in 2.2% of the liver samples. This RNA belonged to the zoonotic genotype HEV-3.

Fig. 6 Incidence of Human HEV by District in Slovakia in 2021

34. Enteroviruses

Enterovirus (EV) is a genus of RNA viruses in which several species affect animals and seven species can infect the human population. Polioviruses (PV) are the causative agents of poliomyelitis (polio), a highly contagious disease that can result in lifelong paralysis or death. Non-polio enteroviruses (NPEV) are among the most common human infectious viruses. They are mainly spread through the faecal-oral route. New-born infants, children and immunocompromised people are the most at risk. While polio viruses damage the nerve cells that control muscles and cause paralysis, Coxsackieviruses cause inflammation of the upper respiratory tract.

In 2021, Coxsackievirus infection was diagnosed in 7 patients in Slovakia, including 6 children with diabetes mellitus T1 and 1 patient with heart disease. During the year, 312 water samples were tested from 47 wastewater collection points. Non-polio enteroviruses were detected in 9 samples, and polioviruses of PV type 1 were isolated from 3 locations, which were confirmed as Sabin (vaccine) like PV strains.

35. Prions

Excessive production of prion protein and its misfolding into a pathological form is the main cause of transmissible, incurable, fatal prion diseases in humans and animals. Prions causing BSE (bovine spongiform encephalopathy) can cross the species barrier. Humans have developed a new variant of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease (vCJD) after consuming BSE-infected beef. There has been no proven transmission to humans of the prion disease of sheep and goats – scrapie. In addition to the classic form of scrapie, there is also an atypical form of scrapie, which has been detected in Slovakia.

There were 27 confirmed cases of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease in Slovakia in 2021. The genetic form was confirmed in 21 cases and 6 cases involved the sporadic form of the disease. The most cases were in the Žilina and Banská Bystrica Regions.

Tests for BSE were carried out on 9,108 samples from cattle. All returned negative findings. The last confirmed case of BSE in Slovakia was in 2010. Tests for scrapie were carried out on 13,286 samples from sheep and goats; the positivity rate for sheep was 0.09 % (atypical form of scrapie), whereas there were no positive findings for goats, which continues the trend of previous years.

36. *Toxoplasma gondii*

Toxoplasma gondii is an intracellular parasite capable of infecting almost all species of warm-blooded animals. Toxoplasmosis has followed a decreasing trend in Slovakia since 2016. In 2021, there were 78 cases of illness, which were reported from all regions, whereas the highest morbidity was in the Nitra and Banská Bystrica Regions.

Tests for the presence of *T. gondii* in food were not carried out. Such tests are not required by law despite the fact that some types of meat pose a risk of infection with this parasite. The State Veterinary and Food Institute and the Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences tested 4,192 samples of animal blood and faeces; their positivity rate was 17.2%. The highest prevalence was in the blood of goats (47.3%) and red foxes (47.0%). There were also positivity rates of over a third in the tested blood samples from cats (36.1%), dogs (38.9%) and sheep (35.3%).

37. *Plasmodium spp.*

Parasitic protozoa of the genus *Plasmodium* are the causative agents of malaria. Their vector of transmission and definitive hosts are mosquitoes of the genus *Anopheles*, 6 species of which are also found in Slovakia. *Plasmodium falciparum* causes the most severe clinical forms of disease including liver and kidney failure, encephalopathy, cerebral oedema and coma. Malaria was endemic in the countries of the European Union until the 1970s. It was eradicated in

Slovakia as early as 1963. At present, all cases of malaria in Slovakia are imported. Five cases of disease were reported in 2021, three more than in 2020.

38. *Babesia* spp.

Coccidia of the genus *Babesia* are obligate unicellular parasites that attack erythrocytes and cells of the reticuloendothelial system of mammals and birds. More than 100 species of *Babesia* are known, which cause babesiosis, a disease that exists in natural foci. Its main natural reservoir is in small rodents. Human infections occur after tick infestation, the incubation period of the disease is 1-6 weeks, and the symptoms of the disease resemble those of malaria, but without the symptom of periodic fever.

There were no documented cases of human babesiosis in Slovakia in 2021.

Out of 133 tests on samples of dogs' blood, 33.83% were positive. *Babesia canis* was detected in one of ten *Ixodes ricinus* ticks taken from humans.

39. *Echinococcus* spp.

Echinococcosis is a zoonotic parasitic disease caused by tapeworms of the genus *Echinococcus*. The definitive host of *E. granulosus* is the dog, wolf, and jackal. Intermediate hosts include domestic and wild ruminants, pigs, horses, and humans. The definitive hosts of *E. multilocularis* are carnivores (mainly the red fox in Slovakia) and its intermediate hosts are small mammals. Humans become infected through contact with animals or contaminated food. Disease can take a pulmonary form characterised by coughing and weight loss or a hepatic form characterised by an enlarged abdomen and weight loss.

In 2021, 8 cases of disease were reported in Slovakia. All cases involved the hepatic form of the disease and the species of the pathogen was *E. multilocularis*. The most prevalent causal in Slovakia was *E. granulosus* until 2016 and since 2017 most disease has been caused by *E. multilocularis*.

Tests for echinococcus were carried out on 719,921 animals, of which 93 were foxes and 719,828 were animals susceptible to infection with tapeworms of the genus *Echinococcus*. Adult-stage *E. multilocularis* tapeworms were found in 5 foxes. *Echinococcus* tapeworms were found in 0.11% of 719,828 examined animals susceptible to infection with this tapeworm.

40. *Taenia* spp.

Taeniasis is a parasitic disease caused by this genus of tapeworms, which colonise the intestines of vertebrates, including humans. A person becomes infected by consuming contaminated food, especially by consuming raw or undercooked meat, or contaminated water. Cattle cysticercosis is caused by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia saginata*, and cysticercosis of pigs by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia solium*, which develop in the muscles and organs of the animals. If a person consumes such contaminated tissue, the tapeworms grow to adulthood in their intestine.

In 2021, as in the previous two years, no case of human taeniasis disease was reported in Slovakia. Findings of cysticerci in pigs and cattle in slaughterhouses are rare. Larvae were detected in 7 pigs and 3 cattle out of 710,005 animals.

41. *Toxocara* spp.

Toxocarosis is one of the most widespread parasitic diseases of carnivores. It is caused by parasitic roundworms of the genus *Toxocara*. Adult roundworms live in the small intestines of carnivores. Parasite eggs excreted in faeces remain infectious for several years. When humans ingest the eggs, larvae develop in the digestive tract that can survive in tissue, but do not develop into the adult stage. Risk factors are close contact with dogs, cats or soil, eating raw meat and drinking untreated water.

The number of reports of human toxocariasis in Slovakia is decreasing. Whereas in 2011 there were 52 cases, there were just 5 in 2020 and no reports of disease in 2021.

The Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences tested serological samples from 86 persons and detected antibodies in 2 of them. Tests for the genera *Toxocara* and *Toxascaris* were carried out on the faecal material and intestinal contents of their definitive hosts in 4,035 samples in 2021. Roundworms or their eggs were detected in 9.12% of samples.

42. *Trichinella* spp.

Nematodes of the genus *Trichinella* cause the serious parasitic disease trichinosis in animals and humans. If overcome, disease symptoms do not return. The main reservoir of the parasite in Slovakia is the red fox, and it is endemic in eastern and central Slovakia. In 2020, there were 6 outbreaks in 5 EU countries which resulted in 119 cases and 1 death.

No cases of human trichinosis were recorded in 2021. The Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences examined serological samples from 128 patients and found *Trichinella* antibodies in 1 person.

A total of 689,425 animals were examined for *Trichinella* spp. and it was detected in 3 foxes. The prevalence in foxes was in the range of 5 – 11% in recent years, in 2021 it decreased to 3.23%. No positive findings have been reported in farm animals since 2009. It is found only in wild animals, mainly foxes. The dominant species in Slovakia is *Trichinella britovi*.

43. *Anisakis* spp.

Anisakis nematodes are parasites of saltwater fish that pass through up to three intermediate hosts. Although they rarely reach adulthood in humans and are usually spontaneously eliminated from the digestive tract within three weeks of infection, *Anisakis simplex* causes severe allergic reactions in humans. The disease is transmitted by raw, undercooked or incorrectly frozen fish meat or shellfish.

In 2021, as in previous years, no cases of human disease caused by *Anisakis simplex* nematodes were recorded in Slovakia. Twenty-nine samples of saltwater fish and fish products were examined for the presence of larvae. Dead larvae were found in six samples from frozen and chilled fish fillets.

44. *Thelazia callipaeda*

Thelazia spp. is a parasitic nematode that infests the eyes of several species of mammals. Two species in this genus can also infect humans: *Thelazia callipaeda* and *Thelazia californiensis*. Transmission requires the involvement of a vector, which in Europe is the *Drosophila* fly. The symptoms it causes are tearing, itching, foreign body sensation, watery secretion and photophobia.

Research so far indicates that *T. callipaeda* tends to create highly endemic areas, as can be seen in Italy, which is considered a focus of infection within the European continent. The creation of endemic areas may be related to climatic or other ecological factors, which are probably responsible for the geographical distribution and abundance of suitable vectors.

So far, no cases of human eyeworm infestation have been reported in Slovakia. From 2016 to 2021, there were 142 reports of eyeworm infestation in dogs and 2 reports of infestation in cats. No infection was recorded in Slovakia before 2016. Epidemiological research shows that two highly endemic areas of parasite circulation have formed in the territory of Slovakia in five years – in the southeast and southwest of the country – with infections accumulating in urban habitats in the two largest cities – Bratislava and Košice.

45. *Dirofilaria* spp.

Dirofilariasis is a disease caused by the species *D. immitis* and *D. repens*. Hosts include dogs, cats, and wild carnivores, while various mosquito species serve as intermediate hosts and

vectors. Humans are a non-specific host. In the subacute form of disease, subcutaneous nodules form on the head, eyelids, face, neck and chest. In the pulmonary form of infection, 1 to 3 cm lesions are formed on the lungs.

In 2021, there were 2 confirmed cases of human dirofilariasis. Whereas all cases of human heartworm disease were caused by *D. repens* until 2020, *D. immitis* was detected also as a causative agent for the first time in Slovakia in 2021. Dog blood samples have been tested for the presence of dirofilariasis since 2005. Tests were carried out on 506 dogs in 2021, with a positivity rate of 28.85%. The most prevalent species in Slovakia is *D. repens*, which causes the subcutaneous or eye form of the disease in dogs. There has been a significant increase in the number of mixed infections of dogs by both species. There is also a rising trend in dogs with clinical symptoms leading to heart failure and cases of fatal disease.

46. *Capillaria hepatica*

The most pathogenic zoonotic parasite of rodents is *Capillaria hepatica*, which has a high affinity for the liver parenchyma. Cases of hepatic capillariasis in humans were diagnosed in the territory of the former Czechoslovakia in the 1960s and 1970s. Nine infections were detected after death, and they were the first cases in which this parasite was confirmed to infect humans anywhere in Europe.

In 2021, the Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences examined 231 potential definitive hosts. Eggs of *C. hepatica* were detected in the liver parenchyma of individuals belonging to the species water vole, yellow-necked mouse, brown rat, and common shrew. The average prevalence was 3.9%. All infected individuals came from the territory of the Tatra National Park.

Annex 1 – List of Cooperating Organisations

Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic – National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with the EFSA
National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
National Institute of Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Diseases and Thoracic Surgery, Vyšné Hágy
Regional Public Health Authority, Banská Bystrica
Regional Public Health Authority, Komárno
Regional Public Health Authority, Košice
Regional Public Health Authority, Trenčín
Slovak Academy of Sciences – Institute of Parasitology, Košice
Slovak Academy of Sciences – BMC Institute of Virology, Bratislava
Slovak University of Technology, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
Slovak Medical University
State Veterinary and Food Administration of the Slovak Republic
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Bratislava
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Dolný Kubín
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Dolný Kubín, TL Prešov
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute, Košice
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary Institute, Zvolen
Trnava University, Faculty of Health Sciences and Social Work, Trnava
Comenius University, Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Epidemiology, Bratislava
University of Matej Bel, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Banská Bystrica
University of Pavol Jozef Šafárik, Faculty of Medicine, Košice
University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
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Annex 3 – List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AHAW	EFSA Animal Health and Welfare Network
ARD	acute respiratory disease
BMC	Biomedical Research Centre
BSE	bovine spongiform encephalopathy
CJD	Creutzfeldt-Jacob Disease
WTP	wastewater treatment plant
DSS	social care home (<i>domov sociálnych služieb</i>)
EEA	European Economic Area
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EREN	EFSA Emerging Risks Exchange Network
EU	European Union
FChFT	Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
HAV	Hepatitis A virus
HEV	Hepatitis E virus
HUS	haemolytic uremic syndrome
morb.	morbidity
ILD	influenza-like disease
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
FoM CU	Faculty of Medicine of Comenius University in Bratislava
CNS	coagulase negative staphylococci
CPS	coagulase positive staphylococci
LB	Lyme borreliosis
LD	Legionnaire's disease
MHD	urban public transport (<i>mestská hromadná doprava</i>)
MI	Microbiology Institute
MRA	EFSA Network on Microbiological Risk Assessment
MRSA	Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
unsp.	unspecified
NCP	National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with EFSA
NoV	Norwalk virus
NAFC – FRI	National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
	National Reference Centre
NRC	National Institute of Children's Diseases Bratislava
NICD	
IoPa SAS	Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
ca.	case
RL	reference laboratory
RNA	ribonucleic acid
RT PCR	Real time PCR - polymerase chain reaction with reverse transcription
RPHA	Regional Public Health Authority
SARI	Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SAS	Slovak Academy of Sciences
TL	test laboratory
s.l.	<i>Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato</i> complex
SR	Slovak Republic
SUT	Slovak University of Technology
SVFI	State Veterinary and Food Institute
TBC	tuberculosis
TBEV	Tick-borne encephalitis virus
IoE	Institute of epidemiology

TSE	transmissible spongiform encephalopathy
DHW	domestic hot water
UHB	University Hospital Bratislava
LPUH	Louis Pasteur University Hospital in Kosice
CCTIA	Central Control and Testing Institute in Agriculture
UVMPH KE	University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
PHA SR	Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
IoZ SAS	Institute of Zoology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
IoVi SAS	Institute of Virology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
VFI	Veterinary and Food Institute
VI	Veterinary Institute
VTEC/STEC	<i>E. coli</i> producing verotoxin/Shiga toxin
FRI	Food research institute (in Slovak: <i>Výskumný ústav potravinársky</i>)
WMRI	Water Management Research Institute
WB	Western Blot
WHO	World Health Organisation
WNV	West Nile virus